

Synthesis and Characterization of Novel 2-Methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl-4-Methoxybenzoates

Haydar Yüksek*, Esra Karakaş, Sevda Manap, Gül Özdemir

Kafkas University, Department of Chemistry, 36100 Kars, Turkey
Corresponding author email: hhigh61@gmail.com

Abstract A series of novel 2-methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl 4-methoxybenzoates (**4**) were synthesized from the reactions of 2-methoxy-6-[(3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl 4-methoxybenzoates (**3**), which were obtained by the reactions of 3-substituted-4-amino-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**1**) with 2-methoxy-3-(4-methoxybenzoxy)-benzaldehyde (**2**), with acetic anhydride. The structures of nine new compounds were characterized from IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and UV spectral data.

Keywords 4,5-Dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one, Schiff base, synthesis, acetylation

1. Introduction

1,2,4-Triazole and 4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives are reported to possess a broad spectrum of biological activities such as antifungal, antimicrobial, hypoglycemic, antihypertensive, analgesic, antiviral, antiinflammatory, antitumor, antioxidant and anti-HIV properties[1-13]. In addition, several articles reporting the synthesis of some *N*-arylidenamino-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives have been published.[3, 7, 11-19] The acylation of 4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives has also been reported.[3, 11-14, 16-20]

In the present study, we present the synthesis of a series of novel 2-methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl 4-methoxybenzoates (**4**) were synthesized from the reactions of 2-methoxy-6-[(3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl 4-methoxybenzoates (**3**) with acetic anhydride. The starting compounds 3-substituted-4-amino-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones (**1**) were prepared as described in the literature [20, 21]. In addition, compounds **3** were synthesized from the reactions of compounds **1** with 2-methoxy-3-(4-methoxybenzoxy)-benzaldehyde (**2**), which was synthesized by the reaction of 2-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde with 4-methoxybenzoyl chloride by using triethylamine according to the literature [22] (Scheme 1). The structures of new compounds were identified by using IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and UV spectral data.

- a) R = CH₃, b) R = CH₂CH₂CH₃, c) R = CH₂C₆H₅, d) R = CH₂C₆H₄CH₃ (*p*-),
 e) R = CH₂C₆H₄Cl (*p*-), f) R = C₆H₅

Scheme 1: Synthetic route of compounds 4

2. Materials and Methods

Chemical reagents used in the study were supplied from Sigma (Sigma-Aldrich GmbH, Germany), Fluka (Switzerland) and Merck AG, (Germany). Melting points were identified using a Stuart SMP30 melting point apparatus with open glass capillaries (United Kingdom). ¹H and ¹³C-NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO-*d*₆) using a Bruker Avance III spectrophotometer at 400 MHz and 100 MHz, respectively.

General procedure for the synthesis of 2-methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl 4-methoxybenzoates (4)

The corresponding compound 3 (0.01 mol) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (15 mL) for 0.5 h. After addition of absolute ethanol (50 mL), the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. Evaporation of the resulting solution at 40-45 °C *in vacuo* and several recrystallizations of the residue from an appropriate solvent gave pure compounds 4.

2-Methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-methyl-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]-phenyl 4-methoxybenzoate (4a)

Yield: 76%, m.p. 160 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) ν_{max} : 1775, 1724 (C=O), 1604,1577 (C=N), 1253 (COO), 832 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 2,23 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2,41 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 3,82 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3,91 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 7,16 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 9.2 Hz), 7,38 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.4 Hz), 7,44 (t, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 7,62 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 8,13 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 9.2 Hz), 9,74 (s, 1H, N=CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 11,03 (CH₃), 23,36 (COCH₃), 55,69 (OCH₃), 56,19 (OCH₃), [114,46 (2C), 115.73, 117.96, 120.03, 126.80, 126.93, 132.23 (2C), 139.50, 149.81, 163.95] (ArC), 144,18 (Triazole C-3), 148,13 (N=CH), 151,61 (Triazole C-5), 164,02 (COO), 166,05 (COCH₃); UV [Etanol, λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 296 (13.680), 258 (27.820), 230 (21.100), 216 (22.430).

2-Methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-*n*-propyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]-phenyl 4-methoxybenzoate (4b):

Yield: 84%, m.p. 157 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 1770, 1732, 1695 (C=O), 1604, 1575 (C=N), 1249 (COO), 817 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 0,93 (t, 3H, CH₂CH₂CH₃, *J* = 7.6 Hz), 1,65 (sext, 2H, CH₂CH₂CH₃, *J* = 7.6 Hz), 2,42 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 2,57 (t, 3H, CH₂CH₂CH₃, *J* = 7.6 Hz), 3,82 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3,91 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 7,16 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 9.2 Hz), 7,39 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.4 Hz), 7,45 (t, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.4 Hz), 7,59 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 8,13 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 8.8 Hz), 9,73 (s, 1H, N=CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 13,34 (CH₂CH₂CH₃), 18,28 (CH₂CH₂CH₃), 23,40 (COCH₃), 26,49 (CH₂CH₂CH₃), 55,69 (OCH₃), 56,21 (OCH₃), [114,46 (2C), 115.75, 118.21, 120.07, 126.80, 127.14, 132.23 (2C), 139.42, 150.23, 163.38] (ArC), 147,95 (Triazole C-3), 148,80 (N=CH), 151,64 (Triazole C-5), 164,02 (COO), 166,02 (COCH₃); UV [Etanol, λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 296 (13.000), 258 (27.740), 228 (21.190), 218 (23.480).

2-Methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-benzyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]-phenyl 4-methoxybenzoate (4c):

Yield: 87%, m.p. 143 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 1761, 1734, 1699 (C=O), 1604 (C=N), 1249 (COO), 817 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring), 788 and 703 (monosubstituted benzenoid ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2,42 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 3,81 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3,89 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 4,05 (s, 2H, CH₂Ph), 7,15 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 9.2 Hz), 7,27-7,29 (m, 1H, ArH), 7,32-7,34 (m, 4H, ArH), 7,35-7,38 (m, 1H, ArH), 7,43 (t, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 7,55 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 8,12 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 9.2 Hz), 9,73 (s, 1H, N=CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 23,45 (COCH₃), 30,84 (CH₂Ph), 55,68 (OCH₃), 56,21 (OCH₃), [114,48 (2C), 115.77, 117.69, 119.94, 126.79, 126.94, 132.23 (2C), 139.62, 151.58, 163.40] (ArC), [127.12, 128.40 (2C), 128.77 (2C), 134.54] (ArC linked C-3), 148,06 (Triazole C-3), 149,52 (N=CH), 151,58 (Triazole C-5), 164,04 (COO), 166,00 (COCH₃); UV [Etanol, λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 292 (13.140), 260 (26.320), 230 (20.500), 218 (22.050).

2-Methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-*p*-methylbenzyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]-phenyl 4-methoxybenzoate (4d):

Yield: 80%, m.p. 150 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 1752, 1735, 1718 (C=O), 1605, 1577 (C=N), 1247 (COO), 806 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2,28 (s, 3H, PhCH₃), 2,42 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 3,81 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3,89 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3,99 (s, 2H, CH₂Ph), 7,13-7,17 (m, 4H, ArH), 7,21 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 7,37 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.4 Hz), 7,43 (t, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 7,56 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 8,11 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 9.2 Hz), 9,72 (s, 1H, N=CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 20,61 (PhCH₃), 23,45 (COCH₃), 30,45 (CH₂Ph), 55,67 (OCH₃), 56,20 (OCH₃), [114,47 (2C), 115.75, 117.70, 119.95, 126.80, 127.12, 132.23 (2C), 139.62, 149.50, 163.40] (ArC), [128.63 (2C), 128.82 (2C), 131.38, 136.05] (ArC linked C-3), 147,94 (Triazole C-3), 148,40 (N=CH), 151,58 (Triazole C-5), 164,04 (COO), 166,00 (COCH₃); UV [Etanol, λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 300 (14.475), 258 (24.025), 228 (27.810).

2-Methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-*p*-chlorobenzyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]-phenyl 4-methoxybenzoate (4e):

Yield: 83%, m.p. 158 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 1762, 1734, 1698 (C=O), 1604, 1574 (C=N), 1249 (COO), 788 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2,42 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 3,81 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3,89 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 4,06 (s, 2H, CH₂Ph), 7,14 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 9.2 Hz), 7,34-7,41 (m, 5H, ArH), 7,43 (t, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 7,54 (d, 1H, ArH, *J* = 8.0 Hz), 8,11 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 8.8 Hz), 9,73 (s, 1H, N=CH); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 23,43 (COCH₃), 30,15 (CH₂Ph), 55,67 (OCH₃), 56,20 (OCH₃), [114,47 (2C), 115.79, 117.75, 119.94, 126.75, 127.12, 132.23 (2C), 139.61, 149.61, 163.39] (ArC), [128.38 (2C), 130.87 (2C), 131.67, 134.59] (ArC linked C-3), 147,76 (Triazole C-3), 147,93 (N=CH), 151,59 (Triazole C-5), 164,04 (COO), 165,97 (COCH₃); UV [Etanol, λ_{\max} , nm (ϵ , L.mol⁻¹.cm⁻¹): 298 (11.260), 260 (22.210), 218 (26.990).

2-Methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1*H*-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]-phenyl 4-methoxybenzoate (4f):

Yield: 90%, m.p. 202 °C; IR (cm⁻¹) ν_{\max} : 1770, 1725, 174 (C=O), 1603, 1574 (C=N), 1261 (COO), 788 (1,4-disubstituted benzenoid ring), 761 and 694 (monosubstituted benzenoid ring); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2,51 (s, 3H, COCH₃), 3,81 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3,90 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 7,13 (d, 2H, ArH, *J* = 8.8 Hz), 7,34-7,43 (m, 2H,

ArH), 7,51-7.61 (m, 4H, ArH), 7,87-7.93 (m, 2H, ArH), 8,10 (d, 2H, ArH, $J = 8.8$ Hz), 9,70 (s, 1H, N=CH); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 23,47 (COCH $_3$), 55,66 (OCH $_3$), 56,21 (OCH $_3$), [114,40 (2C), 115.91, 117.51, 119.99, 126.71, 127.20, 132.21 (2C), 139.64, 151.26, 163.44] (ArC), [126.50, 128.00 (2C), 128.60 (2C), 130.08] (ArC linked C-3), 148,03 (Triazole C-3), 150,33 (N=CH), 151,63 (Triazole C-5), 163,98 (COO), 166,20 (COCH $_3$); UV [Etanol, λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , L.mol $^{-1}$.cm $^{-1}$): 308 (9.730), 282 (18.150), 254 (21.755), 226 (17.060).

3. Results and discussion

In the present work, 2-methoxy-6-[(3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl 4-methoxybenzoates (**3**) reacted with acetic anhydride to obtain six novel 2-methoxy-6-[(1-acetyl-3-substituted-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]phenyl 4-methoxybenzoates (**4**). The structures of compounds **4** were identified by using IR, ^1H -NMR, ^{13}C -NMR and UV spectral data, and the observed spectral values were seen to be compatible with literature values [3, 11-19].

References

- [1]. Amir, M., Kumar, H., & Javed, S.A. (2008). Condensed bridgehead nitrogen heterocyclic system: Synthesis and pharmacological activities of 1,2,4-triazolo-[3,4-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazole derivatives of ibuprofen and biphenyl-4-yloxy acetic acid. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 43(10): 2056-2066.
- [2]. Yuksek, H., Demirbas, A., Ikizler, A., Johansson, C.B., Celik, C., & Ikizler, A. (1997). Synthesis and antibacterial activities of some 4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones. *Arzneimittelforschung*, 47: 405-409.
- [3]. Aktas-Yokus, O., Yuksek, H., Gursoy-Kol, O., & Alpay-Karaoglu, S. (2015). Synthesis and biological evaluation of new 1,2,4-triazole derivatives with their potentiometric titrations. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 24: 2813-2824.
- [4]. Eswaran, S., Adhikari, A.V., & Shetty, N.S. (2009). Synthesis and antimicrobial activities of novel quinoline derivatives carrying 1,2,4-triazole moiety. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 44(11): 4637-4647.
- [5]. Malbec, F., Milcent, R., Vicart, P., & Bure, A.M. (1984). Synthesis of new derivatives of 4-amino-2,4-dihydro-1,2,4-triazol-3-one as potential antibacterial agents. *Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*, 21(6): 1769-1774.
- [6]. Henen, M.A., El Bialy, S.A.A., Goda, F.E., Nasr, M.N.A., & Eisa, H.M. (2012). [1,2,4]Triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline: Synthesis, antiviral, and antimicrobial activities. *Medicinal Chemistry Research*, 21: 2368-2378.
- [7]. Demirbas, N., & Ugurluoglu, R. (2004). Synthesis and Antitumor Activities of Some new 4-(1-naphthylidenamino)- and 4-(1-naphthylmethylamino)-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives. *Turkish Journal of Chemistry*, 28: 679-690.
- [8]. Chidananda, N., Poojary, B., Sumangala, V., Kumari, N.S., Shetty, P., & Arulmoli, T. (2012). Facile synthesis, characterization and pharmacological activities of 3,6-disubstituted 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles and 5,6-dihydro-3,6-disubstituted-1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 51: 124-136.
- [9]. Li, Z., Cao, Y., Zhan, P., Pannecouque, C., Balzarini, J., & Clercq, E De. (2013). Synthesis and anti-HIV evaluation of novel 1,2,4-triazole derivatives as potential non-nucleoside HIV-1 reverse transcriptase inhibitors. *Letters in Drug Design Discovery*, 10: 27-34.
- [10]. Boy, S., Türkan, F., Beytur, M., Aras, A., Akyıldırım, O., Sedef Karaman, H., & Yüksek, H. (2021). Synthesis, design, and assessment of novel morpholine-derived Mannich bases as multifunctional agents for the potential enzyme inhibitory properties including docking study. *Bioorg. Chem.* 107: 104524.
- [11]. Yüksek, H., Akyıldırım, O., Yola, M.L., Gürsoy-Kol, Ö., Çelebier, M., & Kart, D. (2013). Synthesis, *In vitro* antimicrobial and antioxidant activities of some new 4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one Derivatives. *Archiv der Pharmazie*, 346: 470-480.

- [12]. Yüksek, H., Özdemir, G., Gürsoy Kol, Ö., Manap, S., Buluttekkin, S., Gökçe, S., & Alkan, M. (2020). Synthesis, in vitro Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activities of Some New 2-(3-Alkyl/Aryl-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl-azomethine)-phenyl Benzenesulfonate Derivatives. *J. Chem. Soc. Pak.* 42: 624-633.
- [13]. Yüksek, H., Akyıldırım, O., & Gürsoy-Kol, Ö. (2012). Synthesis and *In-vitro* Antioxidant Evaluation of New 1,3,5-Tri-{2-methoxy-4-[(4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-on-4-yl)-azomethine]-phenoxy-carbonyl}-Benzene Derivatives. *Journal of Chem.*, Volume 2013, Article ID 517420.
- [14]. Bahçeci, Ş., Yüksek, H., Ocak, Z., Azaklı, İ., Alkan, M., & Özdemir, M. (2002). Synthesis and Potentiometric Titrations of Some New 4-(Benzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one Derivatives in Non-aqueous Media. *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.* 67: 1215-1222.
- [15]. Çiftçi, E., Beytur, M., Calapoğlu, M., Gürsoy Kol, Ö., Alkan, M., Toğay, V.A., Manap, S., & Yüksek, H. (2018). Synthesis, characterization, antioxidant and antimicrobial activities and DNA damage of some novel 2-[3-alkyl (aryl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one-4-yl]-phenoxyacetic acids in Human Lymphocytes. *Res. J. Pharm. Biol. Chem. Sci.* 9: 1760-1771.
- [16]. Gürsoy-Kol, Ö., Manap, S., Ozdemir, G., Beytur, M., Agdaş, E., Azap, F., Yuca, S., Alkan, M., & Yüksek, H. (2020). Synthesis, antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of novel 4-(2-cinnamoyloxybenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one derivatives. *Heterocyclic letters*, 10(4): 575-587.
- [17]. Bahçeci, Ş., Yıldırım, N., Gürsoy-Kol, Ö., Manap, S., Beytur, M., & Yüksek, H. (2016). Synthesis, Characterization and Antioxidant Properties of New 3-Alkyl(Aryl)-4-(3-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzylideneamino)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones. *Rasayan Journal of Chemistry*, 9(3): 494-501.
- [18]. Yüksek, H., Üçüncü, O., Alkan, M., Ocak, Z., & Bahçeci, Ş. (2005). Non-Aqueous Medium Titrations of Some New 4-Benzylideneamino-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one Derivatives. *Molecules*, 10: 961-970.
- [19]. Yüksek, H., & Gürsoy-Kol, Ö. (2008). Preparation, Characterization and Potentiometric Titrations of Some New Di-[3-(3-alkyl/aryl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-one-4-yl]-azomethinphenyl]-isophthalate/terephthalate Derivatives. *Turk J. Chem.*, 33: 773-784.
- [20]. İközler, A., & Yüksek, H. (1993). Acetylation of 4-Amino-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones. *Org. Prep. Proc. Int.* 25(1): 99-105.
- [21]. İközler, A.A., & Ün, R. (1979). Reactions of Ester Ethoxycarbonylhydrazones with Some Amine Type Compounds. *Chim Acta Turc.* 7: 269-290.
- [22]. Alkan, M., Gürbüz, A., Yüksek, H., Gürsoy-Kol, Ö., & Ocak, Z. (2014). Synthesis and Non-aqueous Medium Titrations of Some New 3-Alkyl(Aryl)-4-[2-(4-methoxybenzoxy)-3-methoxy]-benzylideneamino-4,5-dihydro-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-ones. *Caucasian Journal of Science*, 1(1): 138-148.

